

Synthetic macrocycles – highly selective extractant for copper(II) ions

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Manuscript received 29 February 2000, revised 2 August 2000, accepted 30 November 2000

A synthesis of macrocyclic polymeric form of ligand (A), denoted as [Poly-A] has been described, in which 5,7,12,14-tetramethyl substituted dibenzo-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecatetraene macrocyclic ligand (A) is present as a part of the polymer backbone. The ligand [Poly-A] shows promising solvent extraction properties for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}. The complexation reactions of [Poly-A] with the above metal ions are found to be much faster than those of macrocyclic ligand (A) with a high selectivity for Cu^{II} ion.

Aza-crown ethers have been extensively investigated as highly selective extractants for alkali and alkaline earth metal ions¹. The extraction properties of nitrogen containing macrocyclic compounds have received little attention. A series of nitrogen containing macrocycles has been reported as extractants for heavy metal ions². Among them macrocyclic ligand (A) was found to possess a high selectivity for copper(II) ions. However, the rate of extraction was found slower than those observed for the cyclam derivatives³. It has been observed that the rate of chelate formation of macrocyclic ligand (A) is slow in the extraction process. On the other hand, macrocyclic ligand (A) has also been studied as a reagent for colorimetric determination of Cu^{II}, because the Cu^{II} complex of ligand (A) has a high molar extinction coefficient⁴. The selectivity for Cu^{II} ions has promised to form a stable structure of macrocyclic ligand (A) itself. In this communication we report the synthesis of a polymeric macrocyclic ligand (Poly-A) in which macrocyclic ligand-A is a part of the polymer backbone.

Solvent extraction studies were carried out by shaking a mixture of chloroform solution (5 ml) of the ligands as an organic phase and the acetate buffer solution (0.2 M; 10 ml) of the metal ions as an aqueous phase. Residual metal ions in aqueous phase were examined by atomic absorption spectrometry⁵. In the case of macrocyclic ligand-A, the content of the Cu^{II} transferred into the chloroform phase was confirmed by measuring its absorbance at 382 nm. The complexation reactions of polymeric macrocyclic ligand Poly-A and ligand-A with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were studied in DMF solution. The absorption study showed a shift in λ_{\max} of free macrocyclic ligand which indicates the complex formation. The complex of Poly-A and ligand-A with Cu^{II} showed faster rate of complexation in comparison to that of Ni^{II}. Moreover, the complexation rate of Poly-A with both the metal ions were found to be much faster in comparison to ligand-

A. Keeping these points in view polymeric macrocyclic ligand Poly-A was applied as an extractant for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}.

The pH dependence for extraction of copper(II) has been studied for Poly-A and ligand-A. The concentration of the ligands was ~10 times that of Cu^{II} and the shaking time was 45 min and 2 h for Poly-A and ligand-A, respectively. The extraction efficiency of both Poly-A and ligand-A decreases with decrease in pH of aqueous phase. With Poly-A, 100% extraction was observed in the pH range 4–7, whereas with ligand-A the extraction was observed in the narrow pH range of 6–7.5.

It was observed that further extraction of Ni^{II} by Poly-A and ligand-A did not occur after shaking for 4 h under the same condition as those of Cu^{II}. Moreover, the extraction rate of Cu^{II} by Poly-A was ~100% within 45 min of shaking and with ligand-A it was ~95% even after 2 h.

Based on the observed results it is found that Poly-A has advantage over ligand-A with high selectivity for Cu^{II}. Further studies on recovery of Cu^{II} extracted by Poly-A and extractability of other heavy metal ions by Poly-A has also been studied.

Experimental

Polymeric macrocyclic ligand Poly-A and macrocyclic ligand-A were synthesized according to the literature method^{6,7}. The dianhydride derivative of macrocyclic ligand (A) was obtained by reacting 4-chloroformylphthalic anhydride with ligand (A) in acetonitrile by the slight modification of the method reported earlier⁷. Poly(amic acid) was prepared by reacting the above dianhydride with 1,3-propanediamine in *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) in an inert atmosphere. Upon heating upto 190° under vacuum for ~2 h, macrocyclic polymeric form (Poly-A) was formed. The conversion of poly(amic acid) into poly(imide) was

confirmed by the FTIR spectra : appearance of bands characteristic of the phthalimide ring at 1780 and 1720, and disappearance of the band of the amide around 1640 cm^{-1} . Polymeric macrocyclic form (Poly-A) was found almost soluble in benzene, chloroform and *N,N*-dimethylformamide, but insoluble in ethanol and water. The inherent viscosity of (Poly-A) determined in NMP at 25° was 0.14. The low viscosity and analytical data suggest that (Poly-A) is an oligomer whose degree of polymerization (*n*) is about four.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

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